

Multi-level sub-pixel analysis for object tracking in hyper-spectral image

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Abstract Remote sensing imagery classification has seen various problems such as the existence of mixed pixels. In fact, sub-pixel mapping proved recently to be an effective solution for this problem, whereas it provides a fine-resolution map of class labels from across spectrally unmixed fraction images. To improve sub-pixel mapping precision, we propose a method based on graph cuts. The problem can be transformed into a graph-based energy minimization problem and it can be solved using minimum cut/ maximum flow algorithm. Experimental results with one simulated data sets show the advantages of graph cuts.

Key words: Graph cut, hyperspectral image, subpixel mapping, super-resolution mapping.

1 Introduction

Remote sensing has become an important source of land cover information and it has facilitated monitoring of a large area at a range of spatial and temporal scales [1]. Hyperspectral remote sensing involves imaging a surface through a sensor having a large number of narrow and contiguous bands from where there has been considerable interest in the problem of determining material abundance maps from hyperspectral imagery (HSI). Hyperspectral unmixing is often the first step in estimating material abundances. Several approaches have been suggested to solve this problem and these approaches vary greatly in perspective and technique. Traditional classification techniques assign every pixel to a single class, but remote-sensing images, particularly at coarse spatial resolutions, are commonly dominated by mixed pixels that contain more than one class on the ground [2]. To obtain the subpixel information, soft classification techniques and spectral unmixing algorithms have been used to obtain the fraction of each class in a pixel [3] [4]. However, the subpixel spatial attribution of the different classes in a pixel will still be unknown with these techniques. The subpixel mapping technique introduced by Atkinson [5] can obtain the subpixel location of each class in a pixel by dividing a pixel into subpixels. These subpixels are assigned to different classes by subpixel mapping, with the constraint that the total number of subpixels of a given class is directly proportional to the percentage cover of that class for the original larger pixel [5]. By the subpixel mapping technique, a classification map with a finer resolution can be obtained, based on the fraction of the soft classification or spectral unmixing. In a practical way each pixel is divided into many

subpixels, where S represents the scale factor. The number of subpixels for each land-cover class is then determined by the abundances of the fraction image. Fig. 1 illustrates the principle of subpixel mapping and describes a simple example with two classes. In the fraction image, as shown in Fig. 1(a), assuming the scale fraction S is 4, a coarse pixel is divided into 16 (4×4) subpixels, and 0.25 in the fraction image means that 4 (16×0.25) subpixels belong to land-cover class 1. Fig. 1(b) and (c) describe two possible distributions of subpixels.

Figure 1. Image of 4×4 coarse pixels and possible distributions (scale = 4). (a) Fraction image. (b) 1st distribution. (c) another distribution..

Fisher [6] suggested that there are four types of mixed pixels in remotely sensed images (Fig.2)

- a) Small subpixel objects: the size of the object is smaller than the size of the pixel.
- b) Boundary pixels: the sizes of two or more land-cover classes on the ground may be larger than the sizes of the pixel, but parts of their boundaries lie in a single pixel.
- c) Intergrade pixels: a pixel allocates space for a transition from a cluster of one class to a cluster of another class.
- d) Linear subpixels: the length of a land-cover class may be longer than a pixel but its width is thinner, and the land-cover class runs through a pixel.

2 Related work

Various subpixel mapping algorithms have been proposed. The artificial neural network subpixel mapping algorithms, e.g., the Hopfield neural network [7] [8]. The use of a Hopfield neural network to map the spatial distribution of classes more reliably using the prior information of pixel composition determined from fuzzy classification was investigated. This approach was adopted that used the output from a fuzzy classification to constrain a Hopfield neural network formulated as an energy minimization tool. The network converges to a minimum of an energy function, defined as a goal and several constraints. Extracting the spatial distribution of target class components within each pixel was, therefore, formulated as a constraint satisfaction problem with an optimal solution determined by the minimum of the energy function. This energy minimum represents a “best guess” map of the spatial distribution of class components in each pixel. This technique provides an

Figure 2. Four causes of mixed pixel: (a) sub-pixel sized patches, (b) boundary pixel, (c) inter-grade, and (d) linear sub-pixel [6].

accurate representation of land cover but it presents limits for the prediction of the inter-class boundaries.

Sub-pixel mapping can also be formulated as a linear optimization solution [9]. This technique utilizes spatial dependence within and between coarse pixels where it gives priority on nearby observations more than distant observations. As such, the isotropic variogram is derived from a coarse resolution image. Then, the variogram results are used for spatial interpolation or kriging. This technique produces an artefact, but can be eliminated by applying the mode filter. However, the filtering process tends to eliminate isolated sub-pixels.

Atkinson et al. [10] presented a pixel-swapping algorithm, the objective is to vary the spatial arrangement of the sub-pixels so that the spatial correlation between the sub-pixels is maximized, Following an initial random allocation of pixel proportions to binary 'hard' sub-pixel classes, the algorithm works in a series of iterations, each of which contains two stages. For each iteration, a distance weighted function of neighboring pixels is computed for all sub-pixels. Then, on a pixel-by-pixel basis, the '1' with the minimum value of the function is swapped with the '0' with the maximum value of the function, if the swap increases some objective function. The algorithm is demonstrated to work reasonably well with simple images but the problem with this algorithm it cannot manage several classes simultaneously.

Xiong Xu et al [11] suggested an Adaptive Subpixel Mapping Based on a Multiagent System for Remote-Sensing Imagery, To apply a MAS to subpixel mapping, MASSM is designed to consist of three layers, as follows. In the first layer, feature detection agents are used to detect the different structures in mixed pixels, including boundary-mixed pixels

and linear subpixels. The middle layer consists of subpixel mapping agents that reconstruct features with different subpixel mapping algorithms based on FDAs. The highest level consists of decision agents that coordinate the contradictions between FDAs and SMAs. The advantage of this algorithm is the Support for structures inherent in mixed pixels, such as a linear sub-pixel.

The Markov random field (MRF) is a technique that can be used to model contextual information). Kasetkasem et al [12] used the MRF to generate super-resolution for land cover mapping in remote sensing imagery. Every map is assumed to have Markov property. This approach is based on an assumption of spatial dependence within and between pixels, in which two adjacent pixels are more likely to belong to the same land cover class. Homogeneous regions of the land cover are more likely to be mapped by this model than isolated pixels. As a result, the isolated pixels tended to be ignored. Unlike many other super-resolution mapping techniques, the MRF based super-resolution is not dependent on a soft classification technique. Therefore, the MRF based method is not affected by the inaccuracy of the soft classification.

Many of the super-resolution mapping techniques have a mechanism that can decompose the mixed pixel. With the attention of going beyond the size of a pixel, sub-pixel sized land cover patches could be represented and their location could be predicted with super-resolution mapping. Each approach has limits in terms of improving the mapping as we have already mentioned. In this article, we propose a method based on the graph cut segmentation. The energy function is constructed based on regional and boundary information and it can achieve a globally optimal result. Graph-cut segmentation was first proposed by Boykov and Jolly [13] in 2001. Since then, many varied methods based on graph-cut are developed and these approaches are widely used in medical image, video and natural image segmentation [13] [14]. In this following section, we focus on the concept of graph cut segmentation. Then, we present the results and the efficiency of graph cut in the area of hyperspectral image segmentation.

3 GRAPH-CUT SEGMENTATION

3.1 GRAPH-CUT

In this section, we will introduce the concept of graph cut and how to establish the graph with the given image which will be segmented by the graph cut.

Let an undirected graph be denoted as $\mathbf{G} = \langle \mathbf{V}, \mathbf{E} \rangle$ where \mathbf{V} is a series of vertices and \mathbf{E} is the graph edge which connect every two neighbor vertices. The vertex \mathbf{V} is composed of two different kinds of nodes (vertices). The first kind of vertices is neighborhood nodes that correspond to the pixels and their kind of vertices are called terminal nodes which consist of \mathbf{s} (source) and \mathbf{t} (sink). This kind of graph is also called $\mathbf{s-t}$ graph wherein the image \mathbf{s} node usually represents the object while the \mathbf{t} node denotes the background. In this kind of graph, there are also two types of edges. The first type of edges is called $\mathbf{n-links}$ which connects the neighboring pixels within the image (Here we adopt the 4-connected

system in the 2D image). And the second type of edge is called **t-links** which connects the terminal nodes with the neighborhood nodes.

In this kind of graph, each edge is assigned with a non-negative weight denoted as W_e which is also named as cost. A cut is a subset of edges \mathbf{E} which can be denoted as \mathbf{C} and expressed as $C \subset E$. The cost of the cut $|C|$ is the sum of the weights on edges \mathbf{C} which is expressed as follows.

$$|C| = \sum_{e \in C} W_e \quad (1)$$

A minimum cut is a cut that has the minimum cost called min-cut and it can be achieved by finding the maximum flow which is verified in [12, 13, 14] that the min-cut is equivalent to max-flow. The max-flow/min-cut algorithm developed by Boykov and Kolmogorov [14] can be used to get the minimum cut for the s-t graph. Thus, the graph is divided by this cut and the nodes are separated into two disjoint subsets S and T where $s \in S, t \in T$, and $S \cup T = V$. The two subsets correspond to the foreground and background in the image segmentation. This kind of graph can be depicted in figure 3.

Figure 3. Illustration of s-t graph. The image pixels correspond to the neighbor nodes in the graph(except s and t nodes). The solid lines in the graph are n-links and the dotted lines are t-links.

3.2 Energy function

Many algorithms based on graph cuts have been developed to solve energy minimization problems. Each of these techniques constructs a graph such that the minimum cut on the graph also minimizes the energy. The graph construction is complex and highly specific to a particular energy function. Vladimir Kolmogorov and Ramin Zabih [15] give an energy function, which is defined as follows.

$$E(A) = \lambda R(A) + B(A) \quad (2)$$

$$R(A) = p \in P \quad (3)$$

$$B(A) = \{p, q\} \in N \quad (4)$$

The energy function contains the region properties $R(A)$ and the boundary properties $B(A)$. The coefficient $\lambda \geq 0$ specifies the relative importance of $R(A)$ versus $B(A)$. P denotes the non-terminal nodes in the network flow graph. $|P|$ is element number in set P . $R(A)$ and $B(A)$ are relate to t-link and n-link respectively, $R(p)$ reflects on how the intensity of pixel p fits into a known intensity model of the foreground and background. If node p is similar to node q , $B\{p, q\}$ will be zero otherwise be large. In our case the weights between the pixels and the two nodes (source) and (sink) will be based over the distance.

$$W_i^s = \frac{c}{x} * \sum_{k=1}^N \lambda_k * \frac{c}{k} \quad (5)$$

$$W_i^t = (1 - \frac{c}{x}) * \sum_{k=1}^N \lambda_k * (1 - \frac{c}{k}) \quad (6)$$

with:

- W_i^s :the weight which connects the sub pixel i with the source s
- W_i^t :the weight which connects the sub pixel i with the sink t
- i :Sub-pixel
- x_i :the pixel containing x
- $\frac{c}{x}$:class c presence rate in pixel x
- λ_k :distance between sub pixel i and its neighbor k
- N :Number of neighbors

3.3 Our proposed algorithm

The framework of our algorithm is demonstrated by Fig.4. First, after the acquisition of the image, we apply the unmixing algorithm to extract the different endmembers. After we do the processing of each abandonment map separately and we subdivide each pixel into a sub-pixel with a factor of scale (S). Thereafter the initialization step consists of randomly assigning the sub-pixels according to the presence rate and we obtain a finer dropout map when we apply our cut graph algorithm to it. And in the last step, we do a merge on each new card to have a final card on our image.

4 EXPERIMENTS AND ANALYSIS:

In our experiment, we used an hyperspectral image samson. Each pixel is recorded on 156 channels with a wavelength between 401 NM and 889 mm and a spectral resolution up to 3.13 mm and three endmembers: soil, tree, and water, which is illustrated on fig 5

Figure 4. Framework of the image segmentation algorithm.

Figure 5. Samson hyperspectral image.

After unmixing step we extract the endmembers (water, soil, tree) and then we obtain the following three maps (fig 6 a,b,c) as well as the map obtained after the subdivision of the pixels with a scale factor equal to 2 (fig 6 d,e,f)

In figure 7 (a, b, c) we illustrate the Random allocation of sub-pixels according to the present rate of the land cover with a fine resolution and Figure 7 (d, e, f) after applying graph cut .

In figure 8 (a) we show the final map after the fusion of 3 maps from Figure 7 (d, e, f) and then see figure 8 (b, c) is a scale factor of some border randomly chosen on the map

Figure 6. fig (a,b,c) Map obtained after unmixing.fig (d,e,f) map obtained after the subdivision of the pixels with a scale factor equal to 2

Figure 7. fig (a,b,c) the Random allocation of sub-pixels according to the present rate of the land cover (d,e,f) map obtained after applying graph cut

To validate our approach we used the kappa and the confusion matrix, the kappa index is equal to 0.62% and in Table 1 we presented the confusion matrix with percentage of accuracy

Figure 8. Fig.8 (a) shows the final card after fusion 3 cards from Fig.7 (d, e, f) , fig.8 (b, c) a zoom of some border randomly chosen on the map

Soil	4 33.3%	0 0.0%	1 8.3%	80% 20.0%
Tree	1 8.3%	3 25.0%	0 0.0%	75.0% 25.0%
water	1 8.3%	0 0.0%	2 16.7%	66.7% 33.6%
	66.7% 33.3%	100% 0.0%	66.7% 33.3%	75.0% 55.0%

Table 1. Confusion Matrix

5 Conclusion

To improve the sub-pixel mapping accuracy, this paper has proposed a method based on graph cuts to solve the problem of hyperspectral image segmentation. This problem can be transformed into a graph-based energy minimization problem and it can be solved using minimum cut/ maximum flow algorithm but the unmixing factor remains one of the biggest issues and each time the unmixing results are good we get better results when applying our algorithm.

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